

Scaffolding Visual Analysis in CPAR with Human and AI-Generated Images

Marlon P. Fernandez

De La Salle Santiago Zobel School
Muntinlupa City, Philippines

The rapid proliferation of AI-generated images has raised global concerns over authenticity and artistic authorship, impacting fields from media to education. This underscores the critical need for enhanced visual analysis skills, particularly within the Contemporary Philippine Arts from the Regions (CPAR) curriculum. Despite prior studies on traditional instruction, CPAR lacks structured frameworks to help students differentiate between human-made and AI-generated images, necessitating a systematic approach to develop analytical and creative skills. This study employs a quasi-experimental mixed-method design to examine the impact of a scaffolded Claim-Evidence-Reasoning (CER) framework compared to traditional instruction on students' ability to critically analyze AI-generated and human-created images. Findings indicate that students in the CER framework demonstrated significantly higher post-test improvements in visual analysis across Arts & Design ($n=36$, $d=1.93$), HUMSS ($n=56$, $d=1.65$), and ABM ($n=116$, $d=0.9$). However, variations in post-assessment scores suggest that the framework's effectiveness depends on track-specific cognitive demands. While students in the experimental group reported that CER's structured approach deepened critical thinking and creative engagement, some encountered challenges in adapting to its rigid structure in disciplines requiring more fluid argumentation. This study confirms that structured scaffolding enhances students' analytical and creative abilities when engaging with contemporary visual culture. It highlights the need for track-specific instructional strategies and teacher training to optimize implementation. Future research should explore adaptive CER models integrating AI-driven assessment tools for personalized feedback, ensuring that scaffolded visual analysis strategies are effectively applied in CPAR and similar curricula.

KEYWORDS: artificial intelligence, visual analysis, AI-generated artworks, mixed-methods quasi-experimental design, Philippines

INTRODUCTION

The rapid rise of artificial intelligence (AI) has significantly transformed various fields, particularly in the creation and interpretation of visual content. Tools such as DALL-E 2 and Midjourney are now capable of generating highly realistic and visually compelling images, reshaping industries like creative arts (Göring, et al., 2023). While these technologies offer exciting possibilities, they also pose new challenges in areas such as education, particularly in teaching students how to distinguish between human-created and AI-generated visuals. The growing prevalence of AI-generated images demands a higher level of visual literacy, especially in subjects like Contemporary Philippine Arts from the Regions (CPAR), where students are required to critically engage with both traditional and modern artistic practices.

Despite AI's growing presence in creative industries, its integration into CPAR education remains underexplored. Unlike its applications in fields such as neuroscience and architecture, where AI is used for research and design optimizations, its role in visual arts education is more complex, requiring students to assess both aesthetic and ethical dimensions (Abas, 2019; Page, 2019). Rather than focusing on AI's technical functions across disciplines, it is crucial

to examine how AI-generated visuals influence artistic analysis, cultural representation, and visual literacy development in CPAR.

AI-generated visuals are increasingly integrated into diverse disciplines, demonstrating both their potential and their challenges. In neuroscience, tools such as deepfakes and generative adversarial networks (GANs) provide researchers with customizable stimuli, facilitating a deeper understanding of the brain's visual processing systems (Becker & Laycock, 2023). Likewise, architects have begun leveraging AI to push the boundaries of design, although these advancements require a mastery of text-based prompts (Beyan & Rossy, 2023). The ability of AI to generate highly realistic images without direct human intervention has significant implications for education, particularly in visual arts disciplines like CPAR. Just as neuroscience and architecture must address the ethical and practical challenges of AI-generated visuals, CPAR educators must equip students with the skills to critically analyze and contextualize these images within artistic and cultural frameworks.

The rise of AI-generated images, particularly deepfakes, presents a significant challenge in terms of authenticity and ethics. The rapid dissemination of deepfakes through social media can have immediate and widespread impacts, necessitating urgent countermeasures (Cochran & Napshin, 2021). The use of GANs to create deceptively realistic images of people, including celebrities, raises concerns about misuse and ethical implications, as these AI systems can learn and generate images without human supervision (Greenemeier, 2018). The realism of such images has reached a point where distinguishing between AI-generated and human-created content is becoming increasingly difficult, raising ethical, security, and societal concerns (Shahzad et al., 2022).

However, AI-generated images are not neutral representations; they often reflect biases inherent in their training datasets. Studies have shown that AI models trained on large-scale image datasets tend to reinforce racial and gender biases, such as underrepresenting women in professional settings or depicting racial groups in stereotypical ways (Górska & Jemielniak, 2023; Steed & Caliskan, 2020). These biases influence not only the authenticity of AI-generated visuals but also the way students interpret and analyze them, making bias awareness a crucial component of visual literacy education.

In education, particularly in the CPAR curriculum, visual analysis plays a crucial role in helping students develop a deeper appreciation and understanding of artistic and cultural works (Fernandez, 2022). However, with the advent of AI-generated images, students now face the added challenge of discerning between human-made and machine-generated visuals. Current instructional strategies in CPAR do not adequately equip students with the skills necessary to navigate this complex visual landscape (Abas, 2019; Page, 2019). Given AI's increasing role across disciplines, integrating scaffolded instruction that mirrors approaches in neuroscience and architecture could provide CPAR students with a structured framework for engaging with AI-generated visuals. This growing need for visual literacy underscores the importance of teaching methods that help students critically analyze both human-created and AI-generated content.

Now, if scaffolded visual analysis instruction within the CPAR curriculum can enhance students' ability to differentiate between AI-generated and human-generated images, and a structured CER framework provides a comprehensive approach to teaching visual analysis, can it produce a meaningful increase in students' media literacy and critical engagement with visual content in the digital age? If so, then the findings of this study could support the replication and benchmarking of visual analysis instruction, aid in the development of media literacy programs for other educational contexts, and assist in preparing students to navigate the ethical and practical challenges posed by AI-generated art.

Literature Review

A. *Impact of AI-Generated Images on Visual Literacy*

Visual analysis skills are foundational in arts education, enabling students to critically engage with visual media, from traditional artwork to modern AI-generated images. These skills cultivate creativity, visual memory, and understanding of art principles (Matusiak et al., 2019). Given the prevalence of AI-generated imagery, visual literacy is increasingly essential to help students interpret and evaluate these new forms, distinguishing between human-made and machine-created content (González-Zamar et al., 2023; Ragot et al., 2020).

Traditional visual arts instruction emphasizes observational exercises, formal analysis, and iconography. While effective in some respects, traditional methods fall short in teaching students to critically assess modern, AI-generated images:

- **Lack of Bias Awareness:** AI-generated images do not always reflect objective reality. Text-to-image models such as Stable Diffusion have been found to reinforce racial biases by depicting African American men predominantly in sports contexts, while also homogenizing racial features in ways that may distort

representation (Chauhan, et al., 2024; Aldahoul, et al., 2024). Additionally, women in AI-generated imagery are often portrayed with exaggerated smiles and expressions of happiness, reinforcing stereotypes of submissiveness (Zhou, et al., 2024).

- Lack of Visual Literacy Skills: Many students lack the visual literacy needed to effectively analyze complex, AI-generated content (Matusiak et al., 2019).
- Enhancement of Visual Learning: Traditional methods often enhance visual learning but miss opportunities to incorporate sensory and critical approaches crucial for analyzing contemporary media (González-Zamar et al., 2023).
- Differences in Visual Search Processes: Research shows that novices and experts approach visual search differently, suggesting that visual literacy instruction should be adapted for diverse skill levels (Tallon et al., 2021).

Visual literacy enhances critical thinking, encouraging students to explore multiple perspectives and make connections between visual cues and broader contexts (Adil, 2022). Additionally, interpreting images fosters creative thinking, pushing students to transform visual information into new expressions and insights (Qureshi et al., 2022).

With AI-generated images such as deepfakes and digital art proliferating, students face new challenges in identifying and interpreting these media. The ease of generating high-quality visuals raises questions of authenticity and originality, complicating the evaluation of artistic intent (Lyu et al., 2022; Gangadharbatla, 2021). These challenges are further complicated by biases embedded in AI training data, where racial and gender disparities impact how different demographic groups are visually represented (Steed & Caliskan, 2020; Hirota et al., 2022). This dynamic is compounded by perception biases, where people generally favor human-made art over AI-generated pieces, attributing higher quality and emotional depth to the former (Agudo et al., 2022).

Interacting with AI-generated content can influence cognitive processes, providing creative opportunities but also prompting ethical considerations around ownership and originality in digital art (Lee et al., 2023; Eshraghian, 2020).

To address these concerns, strategies such as dataset diversification and debiasing algorithms have been proposed to create more equitable AI-generated content (Alvi et al., 2018; Deviyani, 2022). Such efforts could enhance the fairness and accuracy of AI imagery, reducing the risk of perpetuating societal stereotypes within visual arts education.

B. *Claim-Evidence-Reasoning (CER) Framework*

The Claim-Evidence-Reasoning (CER) framework has been extensively used in science education, enabling students to develop analytical skills by making claims supported with evidence and reasoning. This framework fosters critical thinking and can be applied to visual arts to help students articulate their interpretations of artwork (Masters & Docktor, 2022).

Research shows that CER enhances students' ability to construct well-reasoned arguments, particularly when scaffolded. Studies reveal that students using CER frameworks exhibit greater skill in formulating evidence-based explanations (Samosa, 2021; McNeill & Krajcik, 2009).

C. *Instructional Strategies for Enhancing Visual Analysis of AI-Generated Content*

In visual arts education, the debate between traditional and scaffolded approaches is significant. Traditional instruction offers a static learning environment that often lacks adaptability, while scaffolded instruction provides temporary support that empowers students to tackle complex visual analysis tasks independently (Cull & Davis, 2013). Research highlights that scaffolded instruction, particularly beneficial for low-achieving students, offers personalized support and gradual release of responsibility, fostering engagement and comprehension (Reinhold et al., 2020; Lombardi et al., 2022).

Scaffolding has a well-documented positive effect on learning outcomes, especially in online and interactive environments (Doo et al., 2020). For instance, research indicates that personalized scaffolding supports self-regulated learning, improving academic performance and engagement (Lim et al., 2023). Findings further underscore that scaffolded approaches are essential in visual analysis, as they allow students to progressively develop the skills needed to critique AI-generated content and engage in self-directed learning (Dorodchi et al., 2020).

Quasi-experimental methods, such as pre-test and post-test designs, are instrumental in evaluating instructional effectiveness. These methods are practical for assessing visual analysis instruction, where competence gains can be measured across intervention periods, helping determine the efficacy of scaffolded instruction for visual literacy (Marsden & Torgerson, 2012; Schneider & Rohmann, 2021).

D. *Contemporary Philippine Arts from the Regions (CPAR)*

CPAR is a central element of Philippine arts education, aiming to enhance cultural awareness and appreciation for regional art forms. This subject encourages students to connect with their cultural heritage, fostering creativity and analysis through artistic expression (Fernandez, 2022).

Integrating technology into CPAR instruction presents both challenges and opportunities. While traditional approaches dominate, digital tools and AI applications can enhance visual analysis in CPAR by offering new perspectives and fostering engagement (Fernandez, 2022). However, balance is essential; educators must ensure that digital tools complement rather than overshadow the cultural authenticity inherent in Philippine arts.

E. *Synthesis*

The literature review highlights a critical gap in visual literacy education, particularly in the ability to evaluate AI-generated content. Traditional instructional methods, while effective in teaching foundational visual analysis, lack adaptability for analyzing modern, AI-generated visuals. The CER framework, widely used in science education, has shown potential for enhancing analytical skills by guiding students to make structured, evidence-based arguments. This study proposes adapting the CER framework for visual arts education to support students in critically analyzing both human-made and AI-generated images. By integrating CER scaffolding in CPAR, the study aims to fill the gap in existing instructional methods, providing a structured approach that can enhance students' visual literacy, critical thinking, and ability to navigate the complexities of AI-influenced visual content.

Methods

Research Design

In the attempt to investigate the impact of traditional instruction and a scaffolded CER framework in teaching visual analysis, this embedded study is grounded in a quasi-experimental mixed method design. Combining quantitative and qualitative data, this approach captures both measurable outcomes and contextual insights (Maxwell, 2023). Quantitative methods involve pre- and post-test assessments to evaluate changes in students' skills, while qualitative methods, including provide a nuanced understanding of students' perceptions and experiences. This design integrates ontological realism and epistemological constructivism, acknowledging an independent reality while recognizing that our understanding is constructed through experience (Maxwell, 2023), ensuring a comprehensive analysis of instructional methods' impacts.

Research Locale & Participants

The respondents were Senior High School students from De La Salle Santiago Zobel School, Vermosa Campus, Imus City, Cavite. This two-phased study was conducted during the First Term of AY 2023-2024, involving bona fide students from three strands of CPAR classes. In the first phase, participants included 2 sections from Arts & Design (n=36), 4 sections from ABM (n=116), and 2 sections from HUMSS (n=56). Participants were selected using convenience sampling, as they were situated in equally divided classes. The decision of some participants to opt out helped balance the variables for statistical treatment. In the second phase, one representative from each class was selected to participate in focus group discussion.

Instrumentation

A. Selection and Generation of AI-Generated Images

The selection of AI-generated images followed a structured process to ensure aesthetic and compositional comparability with human-created artworks. Original artworks were sourced from contemporary Filipino artists, including National Artist Benedicto Cabrera, prioritizing lesser-known works to minimize participant familiarity. AI-generated images were then created using Midjourney's image-to-image generation function (version 5.2), employing AI-assisted image synthesis to maintain stylistic consistency with the original artwork. To ensure visual coherence, the AI-generated images preserved the original medium (e.g., painting-to-painting), dimensions, and stylization, with a controlled stylization range of 300-500 (where 0-1000 represents minimal alteration and 750+ results in excessive abstraction) (Midjourney, 2025).

To ensure a valid comparison between human-created and AI-generated images, the selection process was guided by expert judgment rather than statistical methods, as artistic complexity and style are inherently qualitative attributes. Aesthetic selection was conducted by a panel consisting of the primary researcher (a graphic design and visual arts educator) and CPAR teachers, who reviewed the images for stylistic fidelity and comparable visual complexity. Consensus among experts was sought to validate the selection, ensuring that AI-generated images closely mirrored their

human-created counterparts. This process allowed for a reliable basis for visual analysis while minimizing potential biases in the study.

B. *Scaffolding Visual Analysis*

The study involved two groups: the experimental group, which received instruction using the CER framework, and the control group, which received traditional instruction. Both groups began with an introductory lesson on writing visual analysis, covering key components such as identifying visual elements, interpreting their meanings, and constructing coherent analyses.

For the experimental group, the CER framework was implemented through four levels of scaffolding: modeling, guided practice 1, guided practice 2, and independent practice. Initially, the teacher demonstrated how to write a visual analysis. Students then chose from sample analyses using a rubric based on claim, evidence, and reasoning. In guided practice 1, students selected the correct CER from four options. During guided practice 2, they chose claims and evidence from four options but completed the reasoning using a starter prompt. In the final independent practice stage, students completed all parts of the CER framework independently.

The control group engaged in traditional instructional activities designed to enhance visual analysis skills, including:

- **Compare and Contrast Exercises:** Students compared and contrasted pairs of artworks, focusing on visual elements and thematic content.
- **Writing Counter-Arguments:** Students wrote counter-arguments to given visual analyses, encouraging critical thinking.
- **Group Visual Analysis:** Students worked in groups to collaboratively analyze artworks, fostering discussion and diverse perspectives.
- **Individual Visual Analysis:** Students wrote individual visual analyses, applying skills developed through earlier activities.

Their work was assessed using a visual analysis rubric with components such as formal elements, subject matter, style and technique, interpretation and meaning, and personal response.

C. *Pre- and Post-Tests*

Assessments were conducted during CPAR class time, with each test lasting 45 minutes. The tests featured pairs of images (one human-created artwork and one AI-generated mirror image) for both pre- and post-tests. Students from both groups analyzed the same images and wrote a paragraph-length visual analysis, evaluated based on claim, evidence, and reasoning.

To ensure reliability, four teachers independently rated the responses, yielding a Cohen's Kappa value of 0.82, indicating substantial agreement. Additionally, an intra-rater reliability check was conducted by having raters reassess a random subset of 15% of responses after a two-week interval, producing a consistency rate of 0.86. To address potential biases and discrepancies, a consensus adjudication process was implemented. In cases where ratings diverged by more than one level on the rubric, raters discussed their justifications and reached a final score based on agreed-upon criteria. This approach helped maintain uniform application of the rubric and minimized individual biases.

The visual analysis rubric underwent content validity evaluation by two art educators and an assessment specialist to ensure alignment with the CER framework. Their feedback led to minor refinements in the descriptors for clarity and specificity.

D. *Scaffolding and Student Progress Monitoring*

The CER framework was structured across four levels of scaffolding, progressively guiding students through visual analysis. To monitor progress, students in the experimental group completed formative assessments at each scaffolding level, receiving targeted feedback before the final post-test. These formative tasks were designed to measure incremental improvements in claim formulation, evidence selection, and reasoning articulation.

While the final post-test served as the primary summative assessment, qualitative observations and self-assessments provided additional insights into student progress. Any observed inconsistencies between formative and summative performance were discussed in focus group discussions, allowing students to reflect on their learning trajectory and the effectiveness of scaffolding.

E. *Focus Group Discussions*

To gain deeper insights into the effectiveness of the CER framework and triangulate the quantitative results, focus group discussions (FGDs) were conducted with selected students from the experimental group via Google Meet. Open-ended questions explored the framework's application, perceived benefits, challenges, and potential cross-disciplinary uses beyond visual arts.

The FGD questions were validated by an English teacher, an assessment and evaluation expert, and two art educators for face and content validity. The validation process involved a Likert scale evaluation (1 = completely invalid to 5 = completely valid), resulting in an average score of 4.87 out of 5. This strong rating reinforces the robustness and reliability of the study's qualitative findings.

Ethical Considerations

Based on the ethical guidelines in the Ethical Principles and Practices in Research (Ledford, et al., 2024), parents provided consent via email, and students gave their assent through Google Forms, ensuring all participants were fully informed. To protect confidentiality and anonymity, pseudonyms were used for all student identities throughout the research process. This study was reviewed and approved by the DLSZ Research Department, the School Principal, and the Associate Principal for Learning Standards. All procedures ensured that participation was voluntary, with participants being fully aware of their right to withdraw at any time without any negative consequences. These measures safeguarded the rights and well-being of all participants involved in the study.

Data Collection

Based on the permission of Instructional and Performance Assessment Office and the Research Office, this study was conducted from August to October 2023. The quantitative data begun with the pre-test with the same pair of artworks for both groups and ended with post-test with a different pair of artworks. Then, the scaffolding CER framework and the series of traditional instructions were conducted lasting for a total of 5 weeks. Finally, the qualitative data were conducted in FGDs. The data were further reviewed by the same aforementioned experts.

Statistical Techniques

All quantitative data were analyzed using Jamovi. The study employed the Paired Sample T-test to assess differences between pre-test and post-test scores within both the traditional classroom and scaffolded CER framework classroom across each academic track, aiming to measure the impact of instructional approaches on students' visual analysis skills. Additionally, the Independent T-test was utilized to compare mean pre-assessment and post-assessment scores between the experimental and control groups within each academic section, providing insights into the comparative effectiveness of the scaffolded CER framework. Cohen's *d* was calculated to determine effect sizes for the observed changes in pre-test and post-test scores within each academic track, offering a quantitative measure of the magnitude of improvement. Qualitative data from FGD underwent content analysis using predefined categories and codes, providing contextual insights into students' perceptions and experiences with the scaffolded CER framework. While ANCOVA could have been employed to control for potential pre-existing differences in analytical skills, its implementation was not feasible in this study due to institutional access constraints and ethical restrictions. The dataset did not include prior academic performance or other relevant covariates, and retrieving additional data would have required another round of institutional approval beyond the scope of this study. Future studies should consider integrating ANCOVA during the initial research design phase to enhance statistical control over pre-existing differences. Despite this limitation, the findings remain significant within the context of instructional design. Future studies should consider incorporating ANCOVA by ensuring access to prior academic records or including relevant covariates in the initial research design to provide a more comprehensive understanding of instructional effects across student groups.

Results and Discussion

Pre-test & Post-test Performance of students in Traditional Classroom

The research findings reveal significant disparities between pre- and post-test scores across the traditional classroom settings of three academic tracks: Arts & Design, HUMSS, and ABM as seen in Table 1. In the Arts & Design track, students exhibited a substantial improvement from a pre-test mean of 4.67 to a post-test mean of 8.89 ($t = -8.2$, $p < .001$, $d = -1.93$). Similarly, students in the HUMSS track displayed significant progress, with scores rising from a pre-test mean of 3.82 to a post-test mean of 7.5 ($t = -8.71$, $p < .001$, $d = -1.65$). Furthermore, students in the ABM track showcased notable advancements, transitioning from a pre-test mean of 4.57 to a post-test mean of 7.41

($t = -6.85$, $p < .001$, $d = -0.9$). These findings collectively reject the null hypothesis, affirming that there is a substantial and statistically significant difference in student performance before and after traditional classroom instruction across all academic tracks, underscoring the efficacy of this pedagogical approach in enhancing student learning outcomes.

Table 1. Paired Sample T-Tests for Traditional Classroom

Strand	Group	n	\bar{x}	σ	$\sigma\bar{x}$	t-Test			
						t value	df	p	d
Arts & Design Track	Pre-test	18	4.67	1.815	0.428	-8.2	17	<.001	-1.93
	Post-test	18	8.89	0.963	0.227				
HUMSS	Pre-test	28	3.82	2.16	0.408	-8.71	27	<.001	-1.65
	Post-test	28	7.5	1.79	0.337				
ABM	Pre-test	58	4.57	1.82	0.239	-6.85	57	<.001	-0.9
	Post-test	58	7.41	2.46	0.324				

The observed improvements in the Arts & Design, HUMSS, and ABM tracks affirm the effectiveness of traditional classroom instruction, aligning with prior research that underscores its value in building foundational skills and student satisfaction. Golovkina (2023) found that traditional instruction effectively develops professional skills and competencies, outperforming remote learning formats in this regard. Similarly, Abualadas and Xu (2022) observed that while academic performance outcomes are comparable between traditional and online teaching, students report greater satisfaction with traditional face-to-face methods. These findings corroborate the substantial gains in this study, supporting traditional instruction's role in enhancing student learning outcomes.

Although these findings demonstrate statistical significance, their practical implications must also be considered. The effect sizes (Cohen's d) indicate meaningful learning gains, particularly in the experimental group. However, statistical significance alone does not determine the real-world impact of these improvements. A crucial consideration is whether these gains align with established CPAR learning benchmarks and translate into higher-order cognitive skills, knowledge retention, and the ability to apply learning in practical contexts. If these enhancements contribute to long-term academic success, improved problem-solving abilities, and interdisciplinary applications, they carry substantial educational value beyond numerical outcomes. Future research should investigate whether these improvements persist over time and how they relate to broader academic and professional achievements.

However, prior research also highlights the potential benefits of scaffolding as a complementary or alternative instructional approach, especially for learners with varying needs. Kivi et al. (2021) demonstrated that both teacher and peer-scaffolding significantly enhance vocabulary acquisition and reading comprehension among EFL learners, with peer-scaffolding yielding even stronger results than traditional methods. Furthermore, Reinhold et al. (2020) reported that while high-achieving students benefit similarly from both scaffolded and non-scaffolded curricula, low-achieving students show significant improvement only when scaffolding techniques are applied. These findings suggest that while traditional instruction has proven effective, integrating scaffolding strategies might further optimize learning outcomes, particularly for students who require additional support.

Pre-test & Post-test Performance of students in Experimental Classroom

Table 2 presents the performance difference in the experimental classroom. In the Arts & Design track experimental group, students exhibited a marked improvement, progressing from a pre-test mean of 5.00 to a post-test mean of 8.61 ($t = -9.72$, $p < .001$, $d = -2.29$). Similarly, in the HUMSS controlled group, students demonstrated notable advancement, with scores ascending from a pre-test mean of 5.04 to a post-test mean of 9.46 ($t = -11.5$, $p < .001$, $d = -2.17$). Likewise, in the ABM controlled group, students showcased significant progress, transitioning from a pre-test mean of 5.03 to a post-test mean of 9.31 ($t = -14.2$, $p < .001$, $d = -1.87$). These findings overwhelmingly reject the null hypothesis, underscoring the substantial and statistically significant difference in student performance before and after engagement

with the scaffolded CER framework. This suggests the framework's effectiveness in fostering enhanced learning outcomes across diverse academic tracks, thereby advocating for its integration into educational practices.

Table 2. Paired Sample T-Tests for Experimental Classroom

<i>Strand</i>	<i>Group</i>	<i>n</i>	\bar{x}	σ	$\sigma\bar{x}$	<i>t-Test</i>			
						<i>t value</i>	<i>df</i>	<i>p</i>	<i>d</i>
Arts & Design Track	Pre-test	18	5.00	1.534	0.362	-9.72	17	<.001	-2.29
	Post-test	18	8.61	0.916	0.216				
HUMSS	Pre-test	28	5.04	2.1	0.397	-11.5	27	<.001	-2.17
	Post-test	28	9.46	0.576	0.109				
ABM	Pre-test	58	5.03	2.22	0.291	-14.2	57	<.001	-1.87
	Post-test	58	9.31	0.883	0.116				

While the results indicate high statistical significance, their broader educational impact warrants further exploration. The large effect sizes observed in the experimental group (Cohen's $d > 2.0$ in multiple cases) suggest substantial learning gains. However, the practical relevance of these improvements extends beyond assessment scores. A critical consideration is whether these advances foster deeper analytical reasoning, enhanced problem-solving abilities, and the capacity to apply knowledge in real-world contexts. If the scaffolded CER framework not only improves test performance but also strengthens students' critical thinking, engagement, and long-term academic achievement, its integration into standard teaching practices becomes even more compelling. Future studies should explore the sustainability of these learning gains and their potential influence on students' broader academic and professional development.

The substantial improvements observed in the experimental classroom align with research supporting the efficacy of the scaffolded CER framework in fostering student learning and enhancing scientific reasoning skills. Masters and Docktor (2022) found that preservice teachers' ability to construct scientific explanations, including the use of evidence and justification of claims, improved significantly with a scaffolded CER approach, particularly when written, verbal, and peer scaffolds were used to support learning. Similarly, Homburger et al. (2021) reported that high school students benefited from the scaffolded CER framework, which aided in the development and evaluation of written arguments over time. These findings corroborate the performance gains seen across the Arts & Design, HUMSS, and ABM tracks in this study, where students achieved notable progress from pre- to post-test scores. The statistically significant results strongly suggest that the scaffolded CER framework effectively supports structured learning, making it a valuable addition to instructional practices across diverse academic disciplines.

Differences in Pre- and Post-Assessment Performance of the Participants

Tables 3 and 4 delved into the examination of mean pre- and post-assessment scores between experimental and control groups within each academic section, aiming to discern the effectiveness of the scaffolded CER framework in enhancing student learning outcomes. The null hypothesis posited no significant distinctions, while the alternative hypothesis anticipated variations in scores. Statistical analyses were conducted across three distinct academic tracks: Arts & Design, HUMSS, and ABM, providing a comprehensive understanding of the framework's impact within diverse educational contexts.

Table 3. Independent Sample T-Test of the Difference between the Research Participants in the Pre-test

<i>Strand</i>	<i>Group</i>	<i>n</i>	\bar{x}	σ	$\sigma\bar{x}$	<i>t -Test</i>			
						<i>t value</i>	<i>df</i>	<i>p</i>	<i>d</i>
Arts & Design Track	Pre-test	18	5.00	1.53	0.362	-0.595	34	0.556	-0.198
	Post-test	18	4.67	1.81	0.428				
HUMSS	Pre-test	28	5.04	2.1	0.397	-2.13	54	0.038	-5.57
	Post-test	28	3.82	2.16	0.408				
ABM	Pre-test	58	5.03	2.22	0.291	-1.24	114	0.219	-0.23
	Post-test	58	4.57	1.82	0.239				

In the initial assessment phase, results demonstrated varied outcomes among the academic tracks. Within the Arts & Design Track, the independent t-test indicated no significant differences in mean pre-assessment scores between the experimental and control groups ($t = -0.595$, $p = 0.556$), suggesting comparable starting points for both cohorts. Conversely, in the HUMSS group, a significant disparity was observed, with lower mean pre-assessment scores recorded in the experimental group compared to the control group ($t = -2.13$, $p = 0.038$). However, in the ABM group, no significant differences were found in mean pre-assessment scores between the experimental and control groups ($t = -1.24$, $p = 0.219$), mirroring the findings in the Arts & Design Track. While students across academic tracks may have exhibited differences in broader analytical skills, their baseline competencies in CPAR-specific visual analysis were comparable. This suggests that any observed differences in post-test performance were more likely influenced by instructional methods rather than pre-existing disparities in CPAR-related skills.

It is important to acknowledge that while significant differences were observed across academic tracks, the study did not incorporate ANCOVA to control for potential covariates, such as prior academic performance or analytical proficiency. This limitation stems from data access constraints and ethical considerations, preventing the inclusion of additional variables beyond those initially collected. Without ANCOVA adjustments, the possibility remains that observed differences in post-test performance, particularly in the HUMSS and ABM groups, may partially reflect pre-existing disparities rather than solely instructional effects.

Given the significant pre-test difference in the HUMSS track, it is essential to consider whether this disparity stemmed from pre-existing differences in students' analytical skills rather than the instructional effects of the scaffolded CER framework. Without controlling for potential covariates, such as prior academic performance, cognitive ability, or baseline subject proficiency, the observed differences in post-assessment scores could partially reflect inherent variations rather than instructional influence. Future research should employ statistical controls, such as ANCOVA or propensity score matching, to isolate the effects of instructional methodologies more precisely.

Table 4. Independent Sample T-Test of the Difference between the Research Participants in the Post-test

Strand	Group	n	\bar{x}	σ	$\sigma\bar{x}$	t -Test			
						t value	df	p	d
Arts & Design Track	Pre-test	18	8.61	0.916	0.216	0.886	34	0.382	0.295
	Post-test	18	8.89	0.963	0.227				
HUMSS	Pre-test	28	7.18	1.79	0.109	-6.45	54	<.001	-1.72
	Post-test	28	9.46	0.576	0.337				
ABM	Pre-test	58	9.31	0.883	0.116	-5.52	114	<.001	-1.02
	Post-test	58	7.41	2.46	0.324				

Transitioning to the post-assessment phase, divergent trends emerged, further highlighting the nuanced impact of the scaffolded CER framework. In the Arts & Design Track, the independent t-test revealed no significant differences in mean post-assessment scores between the experimental and control groups ($t = 0.886, p = 0.382$), indicating comparable outcomes following framework implementation. However, in the HUMSS and ABM groups, significant differences were observed, with lower mean post-assessment scores recorded in the experimental groups compared to the control groups. Specifically, in the HUMSS group, the experimental group exhibited notably lower scores ($t = -6.45, p < .001$), as did the ABM group ($t = -5.52, p < .001$).

These findings underscore the intricate interplay of instructional methodologies and subject-specific dynamics in shaping student learning outcomes. While the scaffolded CER framework may yield positive results in certain contexts, its efficacy may vary across diverse academic tracks. Understanding these nuances is critical for tailoring instructional approaches to meet the unique needs of students in different disciplines. Further research is warranted to elucidate the underlying mechanisms driving these variations and to inform targeted interventions aimed at optimizing student learning experiences across diverse educational settings.

The differential impacts observed across academic tracks in the post-assessment phase suggest that the scaffolded CER framework's effectiveness may vary depending on subject-specific dynamics. While the framework supports structured learning, it may not universally enhance outcomes across all disciplines. Masters and Docktor (2022) found that while the CER framework with written, verbal, and peer scaffolds significantly improved preservice teachers' abilities in scientific explanations, challenges arose in domains involving mathematical and computational thinking. This aligns with the observed post-assessment outcomes in the HUMSS and ABM groups, where experimental groups scored significantly lower than control groups, indicating potential limitations of the CER framework in these contexts.

Further, research by Shin et al. (2020) in a ninth-grade biology course found that students' perceptions of hard scaffolding as highly useful correlated strongly with individual achievement, while peer scaffolding supported group performance. This highlights the importance of tailoring scaffold types to align with subject-specific requirements and student preferences. Additionally, a meta-analysis by Shao et al. (2023) emphasizes that the impact of regulated learning scaffolding varies across academic subjects, grade levels, and cooperation levels, suggesting that certain scaffolds are more effective in specific contexts. These findings underscore the need for a nuanced, context-sensitive approach in implementing the CER framework to maximize its efficacy across diverse educational settings. Further investigation is warranted to understand how subject-specific factors influence the effectiveness of instructional scaffolds, allowing educators to adapt methodologies to best meet students' needs in various disciplines. Moreover, accounting for students' initial analytical skills through covariate control could clarify whether these differences were predominantly instructional effects or pre-existing competencies. Addressing this issue in future research will strengthen the validity of conclusions drawn from comparative performance analyses.

Perceptions of Research Participants in the Scaffolded CER Framework Classroom

The perceptions of CPAR regarding their learning experiences within the scaffolded CER framework classroom were gathered and analyzed to assess the effectiveness of this pedagogical approach (Table 5). The analysis revealed several key findings regarding students' perspectives on the scaffolded CER framework.

Qualitative Data Coding and Reliability Measures

The qualitative data were analyzed using a hybrid thematic approach, integrating predefined themes based on the CER framework while allowing for emergent themes to surface from student responses.

Primary coding was conducted by the researcher (author), categorizing responses into structured themes aligned with CER components. To enhance intercoder reliability, two independent research teachers reviewed the coded responses and cross-validated the themes. Additionally, the teachers who implemented the CER framework acted as secondary validators, ensuring that coding remained consistent with instructional contexts.

To further ensure coding reliability, discrepancies were discussed and resolved collaboratively among the coders. This multi-rater validation process reinforced consistency while minimizing potential bias. Future research may explore independent validation beyond those involved in instructional delivery to further strengthen reliability.

Table 5. Categories and Codes for the Perception of Scaffolded CER Framework

<i>Categories</i>	<i>Codes</i>			
<i>Effectiveness of Framework</i>	Improved	Enhanced	Challenging	
	Analysis Skills	Understanding		
	<i>n</i>	4	3	1
<i>%</i>	50%	37.5%	12.5%	
<i>Application in Learning</i>	Structured Approach	Creative Thinking	Connection to Career	Cultural Context
	<i>n</i>	1	3	1
	<i>%</i>	12.5%	37.5%	12.5%
<i>Impact on Learning</i>	Expanded Perspective	Deepened Understanding	Valuable Learning	Appreciation for Arts
	<i>n</i>	3	3	1
	<i>%</i>	37.5%	37.5%	12.5%
<i>Disadvantages</i>	Implementation period			
	<i>n</i>	8		
	<i>%</i>	100%		
<i>Scaffolded CER framework to arts subjects</i>	Positive			
	<i>n</i>	8		
	<i>%</i>	100%		
<i>Scaffolded CER framework to other subjects</i>	Positive	Critical		
	<i>n</i>	7	1	
	<i>%</i>	87.5%	12.5%	

The positive student feedback on the scaffolded CER framework aligns with existing literature on the benefits of structured pedagogical approaches. Students appreciated how the framework provided a structured method for analysis, with Maria from the ABM track describing it as “a structured way to look at art” that enhanced engagement. This

perspective mirrors findings by Shin, Brush, and Glazewski (2020), which demonstrate that hard, peer, and teacher scaffolds significantly predict academic achievement and group performance in inquiry-based learning environments.

The CER framework's structured approach also encouraged creative thinking and problem-solving skills, fostering a deeper level of exploration. Carlos from the A&D track described this process as "peeling back layers of an onion," highlighting the framework's support for inquiry and discovery. This aligns with research by Mamun (2022), who noted that scaffolding promotes self-regulation, exploration, and positive engagement, particularly in online inquiry-based settings. Additionally, the framework enabled students to connect academic content with real-world applications. Samantha's reflection on discussing "the impact of art on business" exemplifies this, underscoring the relevance of scaffolding in developing critical, interdisciplinary thinking.

The CER framework further encouraged students to consider cultural context, broadening their perspectives and deepening their subject understanding. James from HUMSS described this as an "intriguing" process of exploring art's layered meanings, echoing findings by Fernández-Fontecha et al. (2020), who showed that visual and multimodal scaffolding aids students in CLIL environments by enriching both language and content learning. Although the overall response to the framework was positive, students identified the implementation period as a challenge, highlighting the need for careful consideration of its practical integration in classrooms.

This feedback suggests that the CER framework, with multimodal and context-sensitive scaffolding techniques, can significantly enhance engagement and critical thinking skills, though adjustments may be necessary to ease its implementation.

In summary, the findings indicate that CPAR students perceive the scaffolded CER framework positively, recognizing its effectiveness in enhancing analysis skills, fostering creative thinking, and deepening understanding. While both traditional and scaffolded methods show potential for improving learning outcomes, addressing implementation challenges will be crucial for maximizing the CER framework's impact across diverse academic tracks.

CONCLUSIONS

This study examined the impact of traditional classroom instruction and the scaffolded CER framework on student learning outcomes across three academic tracks: Arts & Design, HUMSS, and ABM. The findings indicate that both instructional methods led to improved post-test performance, though the extent of improvement varied among the tracks. The experimental group in Arts & Design demonstrated the highest learning gains, suggesting that the CER framework effectively supported analytical reasoning and structured expression in creative disciplines. However, in the HUMSS and ABM tracks, the post-test scores of the experimental group were lower than those of the control group, indicating potential limitations in how the scaffolded CER framework was applied in these contexts.

These variations highlight the complex interplay between instructional scaffolding and subject-specific cognitive demands. While the CER framework is designed to enhance structured reasoning, its implementation in different disciplines may require adjustments to align with the cognitive processes and analytical expectations of each field. The qualitative data further revealed that students generally recognized the value of the scaffolded CER framework in organizing their learning. However, they also expressed challenges in adapting to its structured approach, particularly in disciplines where argumentation and justification require more fluid and contextual interpretation.

Given these findings, future research should explore adaptive scaffolding strategies that are tailored to different academic disciplines. Additionally, longitudinal studies are needed to assess whether the observed learning gains persist over time and contribute to the development of higher-order thinking skills. The use of statistical controls such as ANCOVA could refine future analyses by accounting for pre-existing differences in student proficiency.

To support educators in implementing these tailored strategies, practical applications include:

- **Adapting CER Components:** Integrate CER at levels suited to each subject, ensuring alignment with specific academic demands.
- **Gradual Implementation:** Introduce CER elements progressively, scaffolding student understanding by starting with simpler claims before incorporating evidence and reasoning.
- **Professional Development:** Provide educators with targeted training in CER applications to create structured, student-centered learning environments for diverse learners.

In summary, this study advocates for incorporating the scaffolded CER framework into CPAR and similar curricula to address the growing need for advanced visual literacy. When strategically implemented and adapted, the CER framework shows strong potential to support students in developing critical visual analysis skills, fostering creativity, and promoting the cognitive resilience needed for navigating today's visually complex, AI-driven world.

Acknowledgements

This research would not have been possible without the invaluable support and collaboration of many individuals and institutions. I am deeply grateful to the De La Salle Santiago Zobel School and its Research Department for their support and for providing the opportunity to conduct this study. Special thanks go to Mr. Chris Balintona, Ms. Mel Bautista, Ms. Annika Santos, Mr. Erwin Reyes, and Mr. Justine Olivarez, the Contemporary Philippine Arts from the Region subject teachers, whose assistance in facilitating this study was essential to its success.

I extend my heartfelt appreciation to Dr. Miguel Rapatan, whose insights into the CER scaffolding framework profoundly shaped my approach and inspired this work.

I am also grateful to the students who participated in this study—their engagement and contributions were integral to the research. Finally, I would like to thank my advisers, colleagues, and friends, Mr. Whizvir Gustilo and Ms. Ailyn Anglo-Ojeda, for their invaluable guidance and support throughout this journey.

REFERENCES

1. Göring, S., Rao, R., Merten, R., & Raake, A. (2023). Analysis of Appeal for Realistic AI-Generated Photos. *IEEE Access*, 11, 38999-39012. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ACCESS.2023.3267968>.
2. Abas, S. (2019). Reading the world – teaching visual analysis in higher education. *Journal of Visual Literacy*, 38, 100 - 109. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1051144X.2019.1574120>.
3. Page, M. (2019). Cultivating Visual Analysis and Critical Thinking Skills Through Experiential Art. *Critical Literacy Initiatives for Civic Engagement*. <https://doi.org/10.4018/978-1-5225-8082-9.CH006>.
4. Becker, C., & Laycock, R. (2023). Embracing deepfakes and AI-generated images in neuroscience research. *European Journal of Neuroscience*, 58, 2657 - 2661. <https://doi.org/10.1111/ejn.16052>.
5. Beyan, E. V. P., & Rossy, A. G. C. (2023). A Review of AI Image Generator: Influences, Challenges, and Future Prospects for Architectural Field. *Journal of Artificial Intelligence in Architecture*, 2(1), 53–65. <https://doi.org/10.24002/jarina.v2i1.6662>
6. Cochran, J., & Napshin, S. (2021). Deepfakes: Awareness, Concerns, and Platform Accountability. *Cyberpsychology, behavior and social networking*, 24 3, 164-172 . <https://doi.org/10.1089/cyber.2020.0100>.
7. Greenemeier, L. (2018). Don't Believe Your Eyes.. *Scientific American*, 318 4, 12-14 . <https://doi.org/10.1038/scientificamerican0418-12>.
8. Shahzad, H., Rustam, F., Flores, E., Mazón, J., Díez, I., & Ashraf, I. (2022). A Review of Image Processing Techniques for Deepfakes. *Sensors (Basel, Switzerland)*, 22. <https://doi.org/10.3390/s22124556>.
9. Górska, A., & Jemielniak, D. (2023). The invisible women: uncovering gender bias in AI-generated images of professionals. *Feminist Media Studies*, 23, 4370 - 4375. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14680777.2023.2263659>.
10. Steed, R., & Caliskan, A. (2020). Image Representations Learned With Unsupervised Pre-Training Contain Human-like Biases. *Proceedings of the 2021 ACM Conference on Fairness, Accountability, and Transparency*. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3442188.3445932>.
11. Fernandez, M. (2022). Evaluation of Arts-Based Performance Tasks in Hybrid Classes. *JPAIR Institutional Research*. <https://doi.org/10.7719/irj.v19i1.840>.
12. Matusiak, K., Heinbach, C., Harper, A., & Bovée, M. (2019). Visual Literacy in Practice: Use of Images in Students' Academic Work. *College & Research Libraries*. <https://doi.org/10.5860/CRL.80.1.123>
13. González-Zamar, M., Abad-Segura, E., & Ferreyra, H. (2023). Visual Arts Education literacy in university contexts. *IJERI: International Journal of Educational Research and Innovation*. <https://doi.org/10.46661/ijeri.5735>.
14. Ragot, M., Martin, N., & Cojean, S. (2020). AI-generated vs. Human Artworks. A Perception Bias Towards Artificial Intelligence?. *Extended Abstracts of the 2020 CHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems*. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3334480.3382892>.
15. Chauhan, A., Anand, T., Jauhari, T., Shah, A., Singh, R., Rajaram, A., & Vanga, R. (2024). Identifying Race and Gender Bias in Stable Diffusion AI Image Generation. *2024 IEEE 3rd International Conference on AI in Cybersecurity (ICAIC)*, 1-6. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICAIC60265.2024.10433840>.
16. Aldahoul, N., Rahwan, T., & Zaki, Y. (2024). AI-generated faces influence gender stereotypes and racial homogenization. arXiv preprint arXiv:2402.01002.
17. Zhou, M., Abhishek, V., Derdenger, T., Kim, J., & Srinivasan, K. (2024). Bias in Generative AI. *ArXiv*, abs/2403.02726. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2403.02726>.
18. Tallon, M., Greenlee, M., Wagner, E., Rakoczy, K., & Frick, U. (2021). How Do Art Skills Influence Visual Search? – Eye Movements Analyzed With Hidden Markov Models. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 12. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2021.594248>.

19. Adil, R. (2022). Use of Images to Support Critical Visual Literacy. *Scottish Educational Review*. <https://doi.org/10.1163/27730840-54010005>.
20. Qureshi, A., Sarantou, M., & Miettinen, S. (2022). Meaning-making and interpretation through personal mandalas in the context of visual literacy. *Journal of Visual Literacy*, 41, 247 - 260. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1051144X.2022.2132625>.
21. Lyu, Y., Wang, X., Lin, R., & Wu, J. (2022). Communication in Human-AI Co-Creation: Perceptual Analysis of Paintings Generated by Text-to-Image System. *Applied Sciences*. <https://doi.org/10.3390/app122211312>.
22. Gangadharbatla, H. (2021). The Role of AI Attribution Knowledge in the Evaluation of Artwork. *Empirical Studies of the Arts*, 40, 125 - 142. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0276237421994697>.
23. Hirota, Y., Nakashima, Y., & García, N. (2022). Gender and Racial Bias in Visual Question Answering Datasets. *Proceedings of the 2022 ACM Conference on Fairness, Accountability, and Transparency*. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3531146.3533184>.
24. Agudo, U., Arrese, M., Liberal, K., & Matute, H. (2022). Assessing Emotion and Sensitivity of AI Artwork. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 13. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2022.879088>.
25. Lee, Y., Park, Y., & Hahn, S. (2023). A Portrait of Emotion: Empowering Self-Expression through AI-Generated Art. *ArXiv*, abs/2304.13324. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2304.13324>.
26. Eshraghian, J. (2020). Human ownership of artificial creativity. *Nature Machine Intelligence*, 2, 157-160. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s42256-020-0161-x>.
27. Alvi, M., Zisserman, A., & Nellåker, C. (2018). Turning a Blind Eye: Explicit Removal of Biases and Variation from Deep Neural Network Embeddings. , 556-572. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-11009-3_34.
28. Deviyani, A. (2022). Assessing Dataset Bias in Computer Vision. *ArXiv*, abs/2205.01811. <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.19950.89924>.
29. Masters, H., & Docktor, J. (2022). Preservice Teachers' Abilities and Confidence with Constructing Scientific Explanations as Scaffolds are Faded in a Physics Course for Educators. *Journal of Science Teacher Education*, 33, 786 - 813. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1046560X.2021.2004641>.
30. Samosa, R. (2021). Effectiveness of Claim, Evidence and Reasoning as an Innovation to Develop Students' Scientific Argumentative Writing Skills. , 7, 135-148. <https://doi.org/10.17605/OSF.IO/2PBWU>.
31. McNeill, K., & Krajcik, J. (2009). Synergy Between Teacher Practices and Curricular Scaffolds to Support Students in Using Domain-Specific and Domain-General Knowledge in Writing Arguments to Explain Phenomena. *Journal of the Learning Sciences*, 18, 416 - 460. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10508400903013488>.
32. Cull, M., & Davis, G. (2013). Students' Perceptions of a Scaffolded Approach to Learning Financial Planning: An Empirical Study. *Accounting Education*, 22, 125 - 146. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09639284.2012.755007>.
33. Reinhold, F., Hoch, S., Werner, B., Richter-Gebert, J., & Reiss, K. (2020). Learning fractions with and without educational technology: What matters for high-achieving and low-achieving students?. *Learning and Instruction*. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.learninstruc.2019.101264>.
34. Lombardi, D., Matewos, A., Jaffe, J., Zohery, V., Mohan, S., Bock, K., & Jamani, S. (2022). Discourse and Agency during Scaffolded Middle School Science Instruction. *Discourse Processes*, 59, 379 - 400. <https://doi.org/10.1080/0163853X.2022.2068317>.
35. Doo, M., Bonk, C., & Heo, H. (2020). A Meta-Analysis of Scaffolding Effects in Online Learning in Higher Education. *The International Review of Research in Open and Distributed Learning*. <https://doi.org/10.19173/irrodl.v21i3.4638>.
36. Lim, L., Bannert, M., Graaf, J., Fan, Y., Raković, M., Singh, S., Molenaar, I., & Gašević, D. (2023). How do students learn with real-time personalized scaffolds?. *British Journal of Educational Technology*. <https://doi.org/10.1111/bjet.13414>.
37. Dorodchi, M., Dehbozorgi, N., Benedict, A., Al-Hossami, E., & Benedict, A. (2020). Scaffolding a Team-based Active Learning Course to Engage Students: A Multidimensional Approach. . <https://doi.org/10.18260/1-2--35174>.
38. Marsden, E., & Torgerson, C. (2012). Single group, pre- and post-test research designs: Some methodological concerns. *Oxford Review of Education*, 38, 583 - 616. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03054985.2012.731208>.
39. Schneider, V., & Rohmann, A. (2021). Arts in Education: A Systematic Review of Competency Outcomes in Quasi-Experimental and Experimental Studies. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 12. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2021.623935>.
40. Maxwell, J. A. (2023). A Realist Approach for Mixed Methods Research. In Y. Shan, *Philosophical Foundations of Mixed Methods Research* (pp. 152-168). Routledge.
41. Midjourney. (2025, January 27). Stylize. In Quick Start Guide. Midjourney. Retrieved from <https://docs.midjourney.com/docs/stylize>
42. Ledford, J. R., Lane, J. D., & Gast, D. L. (2024). Ethical Principles and Practices in Research. In D. L. Jennifer R. Ledford, *Single Case Research Methodology* (pp. 277-291). Routledge.
43. Golovkina, M. (2023). Comparative analysis of effectiveness for distance and traditional learning technologies in the universities. *Педагогика и просвещение*. <https://doi.org/10.7256/2454-0676.2023.4.68854>.

44. Abualadas, H., & Xu, L. (2022). Achievement of learning outcomes in non-traditional (online) versus traditional (face-to-face) anatomy teaching in medical schools: A mixed method systematic review. *Clinical Anatomy (New York, N.y.)*, 36, 50 - 76. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ca.23942>.
45. Kivi, P., Namaziandost, E., Alamdari, E., Saenko, N., Inga-Arias, M., Fuster-Guillén, D., Sirisakpanich, D., & Nasirin, C. (2021). The Comparative Effects of Teacher Versus Peer-Scaffolding on EFL Learners' Incidental Vocabulary Learning and Reading Comprehension: A Socio-Cultural Perspective. *Journal of Psycholinguistic Research*, 50, 1031 - 1047. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10936-021-09800-4>.
46. Homburger, S., Drits-Esser, D., Malone, M., & Stark, L. (2021). Building Argumentation Skills in the Biology Classroom: An Evolution Unit That Develops Students' Capacity to Construct Arguments from Evidence. *The American Biology Teacher*, 83, 104 - 111. <https://doi.org/10.1525/abt.2021.83.2.104>.
47. Shin, S., Brush, T., & Glazewski, K. (2020). Examining the hard, peer, and teacher scaffolding framework in inquiry-based technology-enhanced learning environments: impact on academic achievement and group performance. *Educational Technology Research and Development*, 1-25. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11423-020-09763-8>.
48. Shao, J., Chen, Y., Wei, X., Li, X., & Li, Y. (2023). Effects of regulated learning scaffolding on regulation strategies and academic performance: A meta-analysis. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 14. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2023.1110086>.
49. Mamun, M. (2022). Fostering self-regulation and engaged exploration during the learner-content interaction process: the role of scaffolding in the online inquiry-based learning environment. *Interact. Technol. Smart Educ.*, 19, 482-509. <https://doi.org/10.1108/itse-11-2021-0195>.
50. Fernández-Fontecha, A., O'Halloran, K., Wignell, P., & Tan, S. (2020). Scaffolding CLIL in the science classroom via visual thinking: A systemic functional multimodal approach. *Linguistics and Education*, 55, 100788. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.linged.2019.100788>.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The author declares no conflicts of interest in the preparation or conduct of this study. This research was conducted independently, with ethical safeguards adhered to throughout, as outlined in the Ethical Principles and Practices in Research (Ledford et al., 2024). All data collection, analysis, and reporting processes were carried out without any external influence or bias, ensuring the integrity and objectivity of the study's findings.